

FREQUENCY OF ANGULAR MALALIGNMENT OF FEMUR IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING INTRAMEDULLARY NAILING FOR FEMUR SHAFT FRACTURE

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Abstract

Background: Femoral shaft fractures, commonly resulting from high-energy trauma, are frequently managed with intramedullary (IM) nailing due to its biomechanical advantages and minimally invasive nature. Despite its efficacy, angular malalignment remains a concerning complication, particularly in proximal fractures, and can lead to functional impairment if unaddressed.

Objective: This study aimed to determine the frequency of angular malalignment in patients undergoing IM nailing for femoral shaft fractures and to identify associated clinical factors.

Methodology: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Department of Orthopaedics & Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore, from November 2024 to April 2025. Fifty-three patients aged 15 years and older who underwent antegrade or retrograde IM nailing for acute traumatic femoral shaft fractures were included. Radiographic malalignment was defined as $\geq 5^\circ$ deviation in the coronal or sagittal plane on immediate postoperative X-rays. Two orthopedic surgeons independently assessed radiographs. Associations between malalignment and clinical variables were analyzed using Chi-square or Fisher's exact tests.

Results: Of the 53 patients, the majority were male (86.8%) with a mean age of 33.11 years. Malalignment was observed in 3 patients (5.7%). A significant association was found between malalignment and fracture location ($p = 0.012$), with all cases occurring in proximal third fractures. The type of angular deformity (varus or flexion) was also significantly associated with malalignment ($p < 0.001$). No significant relationship was found with age, gender, side of fracture, type of nail, nail diameter, or mechanism of injury.

Conclusion: Angular malalignment following IM nailing is uncommon but significantly more likely in proximal femoral fractures. This may be due to muscular forces such as the abductors and iliopsoas causing varus and flexion deformities. Meticulous reduction techniques and the use of stable fixation methods like double-locked nails are recommended in these cases to minimize postoperative malalignment and improve outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

notable complication, with studies reporting frequencies around 9% overall, but as high as 30% in proximal third fractures and up to 42% in certain pediatric populations with neuromuscular disorders^{2,3}. Mal-alignment, typically defined as an angulation of 5 degrees or more on postoperative radiographs, can result in functional impairment, altered gait, and increased risk of joint degeneration if not corrected⁴. Key risk factors include proximal or distal fracture location, unstable or comminuted fracture patterns, and suboptimal reduction techniques^{2,5}. The choice between antegrade and retrograde nailing can influence alignment outcomes, with antegrade nailing associated with a higher risk of coronal alignment loss in some studies, though overall functional results are similar.^{6,7} Open-reduction techniques may reduce mal-alignment rates compared to closed-reduction, but are linked to higher infection and nonunion rates, necessitating careful surgical decision-making.⁸ Rotational mal-alignment is also a concern, with advanced imaging revealing significant differences in femoral rotation postoperatively, which may not always be clinically apparent but can affect long-term function⁵. In resource-limited settings, the lack of intraoperative fluoroscopy may further increase the risk of mal-reduction, underscoring the need for context-specific protocols and training.

The rationale for investigating the frequency and determinants of angular mal-alignment after IM nailing is to identify modifiable risk factors, improve surgical techniques, and ultimately enhance patient outcomes by minimizing complications and optimizing functional recovery. This research is particularly relevant as it informs best practices, guides resource allocation, and supports the development of targeted interventions in both high- and low-resource healthcare environments.

Materials & Methods Fractures are prevalent injuries, particularly among

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Department of Orthopaedics & Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore, from November 2024 to April 2025. A total of 53 patients were included in the study based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria using a convenience sampling technique. Eligible participants were aged 15 years or older, had sustained acute traumatic femoral shaft fractures, and were treated with either antegrade or retrograde IM nailing. Patients with pathological fractures, prior femoral surgeries or deformities, or incomplete clinical or radiological records were excluded.

Patient data were obtained from hospital records, operative notes, and radiographs. Demographic information such as age and gender, injury characteristics including mechanism of injury and fracture location, and surgical details such as the type of nailing approach (antegrade or retrograde), as well as nail diameter, were recorded. Postoperative radiographs were reviewed to assess angular alignment. Angular malalignment was defined as a deviation of 5 degrees or more in the coronal or sagittal plane, as measured on standard anteroposterior and lateral radiographic views. An immediate post-op was done to measure the incidence of this malalignment. Two orthopedic surgeons independently evaluated the radiographs to ensure accuracy and minimize observer bias. Malalignment was further classified into varus, valgus, flexion, or extension deformities where applicable.

The collected data were analyzed using statistical software (e.g., SPSS). Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentages were used to summarize the variables. Chi-square tests or Fisher's exact tests were applied to examine associations between malalignment and clinical variables such as age, gender, fracture location, mode of injury, type of nail, and nail diameter. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Table 1 Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients

Variables	N (%)	Mean (SD)
Gender		
Male	46 (86.8)	
Female	7 (13.2)	
Age (years)		33.11 (16.67) (15–77)
Nail Diameter (mm)		114.53 (11.86) (90–140)
Side of Fracture		
Right	24 (45.3)	
Left	28 (52.8)	
Bilateral	1 (1.9)	
Mode of Injury		
Road Traffic Accident (RTA)	42 (79.2)	
Fall	7 (13.2)	
Others	4 (7.5)	
Fracture Location		
Proximal	14 (26.4)	
Middle	21 (39.6)	
Distal	18 (34.0)	
Type of Angulation		
Varus	1 (1.9)	
Flexion	2 (3.8)	
None	50 (90.4)	
Malalignment		
Present	3 (5.7)	
Absent	50 (94.3)	
Type of Nail		
Antegrade	21 (39.6)	
Retrograde	32 (60.4)	

Figure 1. Distribution of malalignment cases

Table 2 Association of Malalignment with Clinical Parameters

Parameter	Malalignment		p-value
	Yes	No	
Gender			0.289
Male	2 (4.3%)	44 (95.7%)	
Female	1 (14.3%)	6 (85.7%)	
Age			0.335
15–40 years	3 (7.3%)	38 (92.7%)	
>40 years	0 (0.0%)	12 (100.0%)	
Side			0.871
Right	1 (4.2%)	23 (95.8%)	
Left	2 (7.1%)	26 (92.9%)	
Bilateral	0 (0.0%)	1 (100.0%)	
Mode of Injury			0.528
RTA	2 (4.8%)	40 (95.2%)	
Fall	1 (14.3%)	6 (85.7%)	
Others	0 (0.0%)	4 (100.0%)	
Fracture Location			0.012*
Proximal	3 (21.4%)	11 (78.6%)	
Middle	0 (0.0%)	21 (100.0%)	
Distal	0 (0.0%)	18 (100.0%)	
Type of Angulation			0.000**
Varus	1 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Flexion	2 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
None	0 (0.0%)	50 (100.0%)	
Type of Nail			0.324
Antegrade	2 (9.5%)	19 (90.5%)	
Retrograde	1 (3.1%)	31 (96.9%)	
Nail Diameter (mm)			0.496

90	1 (25.0%)	3 (75.0%)
100	0 (0.0%)	7 (100.0%)
110	0 (0.0%)	11 (100.0%)
120	2 (7.7%)	24 (92.3%)
130	0 (0.0%)	2 (100.0%)
140	0 (0.0%)	3 (100.0%)

**statistically significant at 1% level of significance

* statistically significant at 5% level of significance

Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the 53 patients included in the study. The majority were male (86.8%), with a mean age of 33.11 ± 16.67 years (range: 15–77 years). Most fractures occurred due to road traffic accidents (79.2%), followed by falls (13.2%). The left femur (52.8%) was slightly more commonly involved than the right (45.3%). Fractures were most frequently located in the middle third of the femoral shaft (39.6%), followed by distal (34.0%) and proximal regions (26.4%). Retrograde nailing was performed in 60.4% of cases, whereas antegrade nailing was done in 39.6%. The average intramedullary nail diameter used was 114.53 ± 11.86 mm (range: 90–140 mm). Malalignment was observed in 3 patients (5.7%).

Table 2 shows the association between malalignment and various clinical parameters. No significant association was observed between malalignment and gender ($p = 0.289$), age group ($p = 0.335$), side of fracture ($p = 0.871$), mode of injury ($p = 0.528$), type of nail used ($p = 0.324$), or nail diameter ($p = 0.496$). However, malalignment was significantly associated with fracture location ($p = 0.012$), being more frequent in proximal fractures. Additionally, a highly significant association was found between malalignment and type of angulation ($p < 0.001$), as all cases of malalignment occurred in patients with either varus or flexion angulation. In contrast, none of the patients without angulation exhibited malalignment.

These findings suggest that while most demographic and procedural factors (e.g., age, gender, nail diameter, or entry point) do not significantly affect malalignment risk, proximal fracture location and the presence of angular deformity (varus/flexion) are key contributors. Therefore, careful intraoperative attention to fracture alignment, particularly in proximal shaft fractures and when early signs of

angular deviation are noted, is crucial to minimizing malalignment and improving postoperative outcomes.

Discussion

The present study was meant to determine the frequency and clinical correlations of angular malalignment after intramedullary (IM) nailing of femoral shaft fractures. Our findings indicate a relatively low overall rate of malalignment of 5.7%, which was also comparable to the other regional studies, one of which reported that Malalignment post-surgery was seen in 6(9.2%) patients. Proximal femur fractures were significantly associated with malalignment of patients with a p-value of 0.014.¹ Proximal and distal fracture locations, as well as unstable fracture patterns, are consistently identified as significant risk factors for angular malalignment, while factors such as age, gender, nail diameter, and nailing approach (antegrade vs. retrograde) generally do not show significant associations^{9,10}

A study done in Malaysia in the year 2017 on 179 patients found that the frequency of angular malalignment after IM nail for femoral shaft fractures was 2.8%. All of these patients were reported to suffer from proximal shaft fractures; however, this finding was not statistically significant.¹¹ On the same note, another study reported an angular malalignment rate of 9% after the IM nail for the femur shaft fractures. In addition, they found a significantly associated unstable fracture pattern as well as distal and proximal fracture location with malalignment.²

Rotational malalignment is a common complication of intramedullary nailing for femoral shaft fractures, occurring in 28% of patients¹²

Proximal femur fractures were also shown to be a major risk factor for malalignment in this investigation. This is in contrast to some previous

international literature that indicated malalignment rates of up to 28% in proximal third fractures.²

Our study's significant correlation between malalignment and proximal fracture location confirms previous findings that angular deviation is particularly likely to occur in the proximal third of the femur fractures due to biomechanical factors, such as the pull of the iliopsoas and abductor muscles, which predispose to flexion and varus deformities.^{4,5} While the current study did show no statistically significant differences between antegrade and retrograde approaches, it did reflect a small trend toward antegrade cases having higher malalignments that also correspond with the results of other studies emphasizing the importance of entry point and surgical technique in alignment.^{6,7} Other factors like age, sex, side of injury, nail diameter, and mode of injury by trauma were also not found to have a statistically significant association with malalignment. This is in line with the previous literature found, where such factors are not indicative of angles of deviations as much as are the patient's eccentric anatomical fracture location and reduction technique.⁴

Malalignment, along with infection, nonunion, and leg length discrepancies, is among the most reported complications of IMN¹³. However, IMN remains the preferred treatment due to its high union rates, low complication rates, and favorable functional outcomes when proper surgical technique is maintained.^{14,15} Static interlocking fixation does not inhibit fracture healing and rarely requires conversion to dynamic fixation. In adolescents and children, IMN is also effective, with low rates of malunion and other complications¹⁶

Intraoperative vigilance for early angular changes is all the more important in proximal shaft injuries because malalignment is an isolated finding in the case of varus or flexion deformity. One of the greatest strengths of this study is its objective assessment protocol in that two orthopedic surgeons independently reviewed postoperative radiographs to minimize interobserver bias.

The setting of the study within a tertiary care hospital in a resource-scarce environment enhanced its real-world relevance by providing a glimpse into practical challenges that intraoperative imaging support may not be able to address. Some limitations

of the study were a small sample size and an absence of long-term functional follow-up, rendering conclusions about clinical outcomes related to minor angular malalignment impossible. The other limitation is that rotational malalignment, which has profound effects on gait and limb function, was never assessed, as highlighted in the most recent literature.

Greater collaboration in research and larger cohorts followed during clinical follow-up would enhance our ability to evaluate both angular and rotational alignment and their effects upon the long-term patient-reported outcomes. Methods involving advanced imaging techniques and considerations involving surgical modification, such as the use of double-locked nails or open reduction in difficult proximal fractures, may also help lower risks of malalignment and raise the bar for success in surgical intervention. Furthermore, developing standardized intraoperative protocols and improving the training of orthopedic teams in resource-limited settings remain crucial intervention areas. In conclusion, it has been noted that although axial angular malalignment is an uncommon complication of femoral shaft nailing, it is significantly higher in proximal third fractures mainly due to anatomical and biomechanical reasons. Careful reduction techniques and thoughtful choice of implant style will greatly improve outcomes and decrease this risk.

Conclusion

Most of the malalignment was seen in proximal fractures of the femur treated with nail. It can be concluded that the proximal segment of the femur has many forces acting via the pull of abductors, causing varus of the segment, whereas the pull of the iliopsoas causes flexion deformity. It is therefore advised to properly reduce the fracture while reaming and try going for double locked nails like the sign nail when treating proximal shaft of femur fractures

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